

Examining the Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools on Higher Education Instructors' Attitudes Toward Artificial Intelligence in the Context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution

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Abstract

This study assessed the relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes toward artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City. The research design employed in this study is quantitative, non-experimental, correlational research design with adopted instruments from Celik's Intelligent TPACK Scale, and Ahmadi Fatalaki and Colleagues' Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale. The researchers selected 100 higher education instructors through quota sampling technique. The researchers used mean, Pearson-product moment correlation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to analyze the data. The results showed that professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitude towards artificial intelligence are evident among higher education instructors. Moreover, the researcher found that there is no significant difference in the levels of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes toward artificial intelligence when analyzed by the demographic profile of the respondents. Furthermore, the results showed that there is a significant relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes toward artificial intelligence of the respondents of the study. With these results, further research needs to investigate the particular elements that foster the growth of professional knowledge and positive attitudes on artificial intelligence in the classroom. Studies using longitudinal approach may shed light on how these factors alter as AI technologies advance and spread in educational environments. Qualitative research on the experiences and perspectives of educators may also shed more light on the potential and difficulties associated with integrating AI.

Keywords: *Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of AI-based Tools, Attitudes toward Artificial Intelligence, TPACK Framework, Higher Education Instructors, Davao City.*

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Introduction

Our society is already in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, characterized by rapid improvement in all aspects brought about by technological advancement and innovations. The education sector is one of the recipients of these changes as it also adopted technological innovation to its ongoing transformative paradigm shift. One of the tenets of this educational development is the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), which enables unexpected challenges and opportunities in higher education. The incorporation of AI-based tools in education to enhance teaching and learning has significantly increased in the past years, thus, investigating the ethical considerations in its application is important. Ethical issues encompassing privacy, biases, and the responsible use of the artificial intelligence system are just a few points to dig deeper in this paper. It is imperative to understand how instructors of tertiary education perceive and integrate AI into their teaching practices, being one of the key stakeholders in the educational process, is crucial for fostering a responsible and ethically sound implementation of these technologies.

In France, the study conducted by Cojean, Brun, Amadieu, & Dessus (2023) discussed how teachers' behavior towards the use of AI tools in tertiary education see the use of AI-based tools in education towards ethical integration means facing issues such as issues relating to privacy, transparency and ethical guidelines. But despite these concerns, teachers still perceive using AI-based tools as important and beneficial as it lessens their workloads. Moreover, the factors influencing Filipino teachers' acceptance of ICT-based instruction have been the subject of several research. Kim & Lee (2022) discovered that although behavioral intention, ICT use habit, and enabling factors influence actual use, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and education policy greatly impact teachers' intention to use ICTs. In addition, according to Nueva (2019), Filipino teachers have a positive attitude toward technology, and perceived usability is strongly correlated with technology integration practices. All of these studies point to the need for a comprehensive model that takes into account social influence, education policy, technological pedagogical expectations, digital adoption, age, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and attitude toward technology to predict Filipino teachers' adoption of ICT-based instruction.

In the local context, studies about ethical integration and behavior in tertiary education have been quite limited. With this, the researchers would like to explore more on this study in the local setup. Moreover, this research aims to shed light on the crucial role that professional knowledge plays in defining the ethical aspects of AI integration in higher education as we navigate the complexities of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This served as a basis for future research, policy development, and educational practices in an era characterized by technological innovation and ethical imperatives.

This study aims to determine the significance on the relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitude towards artificial intelligence. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following: (1) What is the level of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools among higher education instructors in Davao City when analyzed in terms of intelligent technological knowledge, intelligent technological and pedagogical knowledge, intelligent technological and content knowledge, intelligent technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, and ethics?; (2) What is the level of attitude toward artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City when analyzed in terms of interest, ethical concerns, intention to use, usefulness for teachers, and usefulness for learners?; (3) Is there a significant difference between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools among higher education instructors in Davao City when analyzed by length of service, and areas of discipline? (4) Is there a significant difference between attitudes toward artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City when analyzed by length of service, and areas of discipline? (5) Is there a significant relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitude towards artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City?

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance: There is no significant relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitude towards artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City.

This study is grounded in the TPACK Framework of Mishra and Koehler (2006). Mishra and Koehler (2006) extended PCK by incorporating technological knowledge (TK) to better understand teachers' knowledge for effective technology integration. The extension process yielded technological content knowledge (TCK), technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK), and technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). Since TPACK is a flexible and broad framework (Mishra et al., 2010) several researchers adopted TPACK for different technological tools and pedagogical methods. For instance, Lee and Tsai (2010) determined knowledge to use web technologies in the scope of TPACK. Further, Valtonen et al. (2017) adopted TPACK for teaching twenty-first-century skills such as critical thinking and collaboration. The current study addresses the knowledge and skills to use AI-based tools. Hence, we focused on TK-related knowledge components, namely, TK, TCK, TPK, and TPACK.

Materials and Methods

The researchers employ quantitative, nonexperimental, correlational research design to determine the outcomes of the study. Quantitative research design uses statistical data to examine the relationships between and among variables through surveys and experiments which further produces objective and empirical data (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). Furthermore, nonexperimental research assesses phenomena without direct manipulation of the variables in the given study. Moreover, there are two main types of nonexperimental research design wherein one of the types of this design is employed in the study. Correlational design evaluates the relationships of two or more variables in a study (Frey, 2018). The following research designs are employed to answer the hypotheses of the study. Using these designs, the researchers provided quantifiable data about the level of professional knowledge on the ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes towards artificial intelligence. Furthermore, it seeks to provide statistical data about the relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes towards artificial intelligence among higher education instructors in Davao City. Through the statistical data collected and analyzed, the researchers further aim to create a learning development plan that is anchored to the statistical results of this study.

Using a quota sampling technique, the researchers chose 100 Higher Education Instructors in Davao City. Respondents were gathered from all Davao City public and private postsecondary educational institutions. The following qualifications must be met in order for a person to be accepted as a respondent for this study: they must be male or female, between the ages of 23 and 65, and working in any reputable Davao City public and private colleges and universities. The following reasons prevented the respondents from being included in the study: they are not instructors at any accredited public or private educational establishment in the area, and their age does not fall within the above-mentioned age range.

The researchers used the following adopted scales: Celik's Intelligent TPACK Scale, and Ahmadi Fatalaki and Colleagues' Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale. Celik's Intelligent TPACK scale was created to assess teachers' AI-based decisions based on technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) framework with ethical aspects (Celik, 2023). This scale is composed of 27 items which were further divided into 5 indicators namely; intelligent technological knowledge (TK) with 5 items, intelligent technological-pedagogical knowledge (TPK) with 7 items; intelligent technological-content knowledge (TCK) with 4 items; intelligent technological, pedagogical, content knowledge (TPACK) with 7 items; and ethics with 4 items. Ahmadi Fatalaki's Attitudes Towards Artificial Intelligence scale was developed to measure the teacher's attitude toward applying AI and its integration into educational practices (Fatalaki, Saedi, Marand, & Firuz, 2024). This scale is composed of 28 items which were further divided into 5 indicators namely; interest with 6 items; ethical concerns with 6 items; intention to use with 5 items; usefulness for teachers with 5 items; and usefulness for learners with 6 items.

To determine the levels of professional knowledge on the ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes towards artificial intelligence, the researchers employed the statistical tool called “mean”. Furthermore, to determine the significant difference of each variable on the demographic profile of the study, the researchers employed “Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Moreover, to determine the relationship between professional knowledge on the ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitudes towards artificial intelligence, the researchers employed a statistical tool called “Pearson product-moment correlation or Pearson-r”. Through the use of IBM-SPSS Statistics 26, the data collected were statistically treated. After, the treated data were further analyzed and interpreted by the researchers.

The researchers abided by the guidelines established by the Research Ethics Committee of their affiliated institution. These guidelines encompass various assessment criteria, including but not limited to social value, informed consent, risk, benefits, and safety, privacy and confidentiality, justice, transparency, qualification of researchers, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement. Furthermore, these protocols abide by standards outlined by the Department of Science and Technology – Philippine Health Research and Ethics Board (DOST-PHREB) under the Republic Act No. 10532, also known as the Philippine National Health Research System (PNHRS) Act of 2013. The researchers are committed to ensuring that all participants in the study are treated with the utmost respect and provided with the necessary protection, recognizing these elements as pivotal to the study's success.

The researchers adhered to the following steps before the conduct of data gathering of this study. First, the researchers sent a concept paper for approval of this study to the professor of the course, Advance Educational Planning. Second, upon approval of the study, the researchers adopted the research instruments namely; Celik’s Intelligent TPACK Scale and, Fatalaki and Colleague’s Attitudes Towards Artificial Intelligence Scale. Third, the researchers asked for the approval of the conduct of the study by the institutional Research Ethics Committee (REC) before the data gathering commences. Fourth, the researchers created an online form through Google Forms containing the informed consent form and data privacy notice prior to the administration of the adopted research instruments. Lastly, the researchers asked various higher education institutions in Davao City through a communication letter about the research study and its call for respondents.

Results

This section presents the study’s results after the data gathering and analysis. A discussion was added to supplement the data gathered and explained further by various literature supporting the study’s results.

Table 1. Summary of the Level of Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools of Higher Education Instructors

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Intelligent Technological Knowledge	3.16	High
Intelligent Technological and Pedagogical Knowledge	3.36	High
Intelligent Technological and Content Knowledge	3.15	High
Intelligent Technological, Pedagogical, And Content Knowledge	3.15	High
Ethics	3.33	High
Overall	3.28	High

Table 1 shows the summary of the level of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools of higher education instructors. The following domains under the said variable are intelligent technological knowledge, intelligent technological and pedagogical knowledge, intelligent technological and content knowledge, intelligent technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, and ethics. Among the domains under the said variable, intelligent technological and pedagogical knowledge got the highest mean of 3.36, or high. Furthermore, the overall professional knowledge on ethical

integration of artificial intelligence-based tools got a mean score of 3.28, or high which indicates that professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools is evident among higher education instructors.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Attitude toward Artificial Intelligence of Higher Education Instructors

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Interest	3.22	High
Ethical Concerns	3.13	High
Intention to Use	3.21	High
Usefulness for Teachers	3.14	High
Usefulness for Learners	3.13	High
Overall	3.17	High

Table 2 shows the summary of the level of attitude toward artificial intelligence of higher education instructors. The following domains under this variable are interest, ethical concerns, intention to use, usefulness for teachers, and usefulness for learners. Among the domains under this variable, interest got the highest mean of 3.22, or high. Furthermore, overall attitude toward artificial intelligence got a mean score of 3.17 or high which indicates that attitude toward artificial intelligence is evident among higher education instructors.

Table 3.1 Test of Significance in the Difference on the Level of Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools when Analyzed by Length of Service

Factor	Length of Service							F	Significance	Decision on H ₀
	1-3 years	4-6 years	7-9 years	10-12 years	13-15 years	16 years above	Total			
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean			
Intelligent Technological Knowledge	3.16	3.18	3.09	3.23	3.16	3.22	3.16	.358	.876	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological and Pedagogical Knowledge	3.27	3.36	3.38	3.40	3.48	3.27	3.36	.660	.654	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological and Content Knowledge	3.08	3.15	3.22	3.15	3.05	3.05	3.15	.395	.851	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological, Pedagogical, And Content Knowledge	2.98	3.28	3.10	3.19	3.03	3.04	3.15	2.171	.064	Fail to Reject
Ethics	3.41	3.29	3.38	3.40	3.10	3.27	3.33	.534	.750	Fail to Reject
Overall	3.28	3.28	3.28	3.35	3.25	3.25	3.28	.267	.930	Fail to Reject

Note: *P<0.05

As illustrated in Table 3.1 showing the results of the significant difference in the level of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools when analyzed by length of service, the overall significant value (p-value) is .930. It means that there is no significant difference in the levels of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools when analyzed by length of service. It implies that respondents who have a length of service as higher education instructors from 1-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-9 years, 10-12 years, 13-15 years, and 16 years above have no differences in

terms of their perception of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools. Based on the table, the domains under professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools fail to reject the null hypothesis as shown in their p-value which is greater than .05. This means that there is no significant difference between the length of service of 1-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-9 years, 10-12 years, 13-15 years, and 16 years above on the perception of individual domains stated under professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools.

Table 3.2 Test of Significance in the Difference on the Level of Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools when Analyzed by Areas of Discipline

Factor	Areas of Discipline					F	Significance	Decision on H ₀
	Teacher Education	Business & Management Education	Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication	Tourism & Hospitality Management Education	Total			
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean			
Intelligent Technological Knowledge	3.16	3.13	3.16	3.25	3.16	.370	.775	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological and Pedagogical Knowledge	3.33	3.32	3.39	3.42	3.36	.501	.682	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological and Content Knowledge	3.15	3.13	3.20	3.08	3.15	.241	.868	Fail to Reject
Intelligent Technological, Pedagogical, And Content Knowledge	3.21	3.10	3.08	3.21	3.15	.988	.402	Fail to Reject
Ethics	3.34	3.27	3.288	3.46	3.33	.582	.626	Fail to Reject
Overall	3.28	3.24	3.28	3.38	3.28	1.315	.274	Fail to Reject

Note: *P<0.05

As illustrated in Table 3.2 showing the results of the significant difference in the level of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools when analyzed by areas of discipline, the overall significant value (p-value) is .274. It means that there is no significant difference in the levels of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools when analyzed by areas of discipline. It implies that respondents coming from different areas of discipline (Teacher Education, Business & Management Education, Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication, and Hospitality and Tourism Management Education) have no differences in terms of their perception of professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools. Based on the table, the domains under professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools fail to reject the null hypothesis as shown in their p-value which is greater than .05. This means that there is no significant difference among the different areas of discipline on the perception of individual domains stated under professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools.

Table 4.1 Test of Significance in the Difference on the Level of Attitude toward Artificial Intelligence when Analyzed by Length of Service

Factor	Length of Service							F	Significance	Decision on H ₀
	1-3 years	4-6 years	7-9 years	10-12 years	13-15 years	16 years above	Total			
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean			
Interest	3.27	3.21	3.20	3.27	3.12	3.31	3.22	.262	.932	Fail to Reject
Ethical Concerns	2.91	3.12	3.17	3.39	3.20	3.00	3.13	1.988	.087	Fail to Reject
Intention to Use	3.05	3.26	3.20	3.23	3.16	3.24	3.21	.398	.849	Fail to Reject
Usefulness for Teachers	3.18	3.05	3.22	3.09	3.36	3.20	3.14	.939	.460	Fail to Reject
Usefulness for Learners	3.10	3.12	3.08	3.31	3.23	3.11	3.13	.653	.660	Fail to Reject
Overall	3.08	3.17	3.16	3.30	3.18	3.16	3.17	1.267	.285	Fail to Reject

Note: *P<0.05

As illustrated in Table 4.1 showing the results of the significant difference in the level of attitude toward artificial intelligence when analyzed by length of service, the overall significant value (p-value) is .285. It means that there is no significant difference in the levels of attitude toward artificial intelligence when analyzed by length of service. It implies that respondents who have a length of service as higher education instructors from 1-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-9 years, 10-12 years, 13-15 years, and 16 years above have no differences in terms of their attitude toward artificial intelligence. Based on the table, the domains under attitude toward artificial intelligence fail to reject the null hypothesis as shown in their p-value which is greater than .05. This means that there is no significant difference between the length of service of 1-3 years, 4-6 years, 7-9 years, 10-12 years, 13-15 years, and 16 years above on the perception of individual domains stated under attitude toward artificial intelligence.

Table 4.2 Test of Significance in the Difference on the Level of Attitude toward Artificial Intelligence when Analyzed by Areas of Discipline

Factor	Areas of Discipline					F	Significance	Decision on H ₀
	Teacher Education	Business & Management Education	Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication	Tourism & Hospitality Management Education	Total			
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean			
Interest	3.20	3.32	3.22	3.10	3.22	1.128	.342	Fail to Reject
Ethical Concerns	3.08	3.21	3.15	3.09	3.13	.555	.646	Fail to Reject
Intention to Use	3.22	3.34	3.13	3.04	3.21	1.602	.194	Fail to Reject
Usefulness for Teachers	3.06	3.20	3.17	3.21	3.14	.867	.461	Fail to Reject
Usefulness for Learners	3.24	3.04	3.09	3.10	3.13	1.722	.168	Fail to Reject
Overall	3.19	3.23	3.15	3.08	3.17	1.695	.173	Fail to Reject

Note: *P<0.05

As illustrated in Table 4.2 showing the results of the significant difference in the level of attitude toward artificial intelligence when analyzed by areas of discipline, the overall significant value (p-value) is .173. It means that there is no significant difference in the levels of attitude toward artificial intelligence when analyzed by areas of discipline. It implies that respondents coming from different areas of discipline (Teacher Education, Business & Management Education, Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication, and Hospitality and Tourism Management Education) have no differences in terms of their perception of attitudes toward artificial intelligence. Based on the table, the domains under attitude toward artificial intelligence fail to reject the null hypothesis as shown in their p-value which is greater than .05. This means that there is no significant difference among the different areas of discipline on the perception of individual domains stated under attitude toward artificial intelligence.

Table 5. Test of Significance in the Relationship between Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools and Attitude toward Artificial Intelligence of Higher Education Instructors

	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	Attitude toward Artificial Intelligence of Higher Education Instructors			
Professional Knowledge on Ethical Integration of Artificial Intelligence-Based Tools of Higher Education Instructors	.238	.017*	Reject	Significant

Note: *P<0.05

As reflected in Table 5, it shows the significant relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and the attitude toward artificial intelligence of higher education instructors. The result exhibits that the relationship between professional knowledge on ethical integration of artificial intelligence-based tools and attitude toward artificial intelligence is significant. It implies that the relationship of the two variables of the study shows a significant relationship. With an overall p-value of .017 which is less than 0.05, the relationship is significant at α 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Furthermore, the overall correlation coefficient of .238 shows that the relationship is very weak or has very little correlation.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide insights into higher education instructors' professional knowledge and attitudes in regard to ethical integration. Such findings expand the developing body of research on AI in education and provide key implications for policy and practice.

Results show that the respondents, higher education instructors, have a high level of professional knowledge in integrating AI-based tools in an ethical manner. This supports the findings of Zhai et al., who found that educators from higher education institutions increasingly become more aware and gain insight into how they integrated AI into their teaching practices. The highest score was recorded in the intelligent technological and pedagogical knowledge domain indicating a high level of knowledge at the point of intersection between AI technology and pedagogical practices. This is relatively encouraging, as it shows that educators are well-positioned to leverage such AI tools in their teaching with effectiveness. With such rapid development of AI, however, professional training will have to be provided on a continuous basis. As Holmes et al. (2019) note, "Each educator's AI-related competencies will have to be maintained and developed through ongoing training and support."

The framework of the TPACK concept provides a useful lens for understanding the role of AI in education. A high score in intelligent technological and pedagogical knowledge would mean a baseline that educators are building a foundation in what might be termed "AI-TPACK". Chai et al. (2019) argue that meaningful integration of any technology in education requires a balance between technological,

pedagogical, and content knowledge. Future research might wish to probe how AI-specific TPACK develops and influences teaching practices.

The attitude of the instructors of higher education in the use of AI was also measured using statements, and a positive attitude was expressed. The highest score was attained by the domain showing a very high interest and enthusiasm in AI by educators. This result agrees with that of Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), who noted an increasing interest in AI applications among professionals in higher education. Positive attitudes toward AI are necessary for the successful integration of such technologies into an educational context. As Chin and Wang (2021) aver, educators' attitudes level largely reflects their intention to adopt and effectively use AI-based tools in their teaching practices. Thus, the high level of interest observed in this study forms a good ground for implementing AI initiatives at the higher education level. However, it should also be noted that while interest is high, other domains such as ethical concerns and intention to use have relatively lower mean scores. This agrees with Lim et al.'s study, in which the ethical consideration was found to be one of the key inhibitors in the adoption of AI in education. Future professional development should therefore focus on such ethical concerns for further improvement in attitude and for better adoption rates.

Surprisingly, professional knowledge or attitudes did not differ so much according to length of service or areas of discipline. This runs somewhat contrary to findings by some previous research, such as that by Bao et al. (2013), as cited by Ulfert-Blank and Schmidt (2022): variation in AI adoption according to teaching experience and subject area. The fact that no significant differences are observed suggests successful institutional efforts towards equal AI-related training and resource provision across disciplines. On the other hand, the use of AI in higher education can still be considered to be in its relative infancy, where educators on the whole would share similar levels of knowledge and attitude. However, this again raises questions with respect to the depth of AI integration across different disciplines. For example, Luckin and Cukurova (2019) consider that AI in education needs to be context-specific and differentiated based on subject-specific needs. A lack of significant disciplinary differences may point toward a requirement for domain-specific AI training and applications.

The study showed that professional knowledge of the ethical integration of AI-based tools correlated slightly but significantly with attitude towards AI. This finding corroborates adaptations of TAM to AI use in education: according to TAM, perceived usefulness and ease of use or knowledge of the subject influence attitude towards technology adoption (Abdullah et al., 2021). Although the correlation is weak, it gives insight into possible ways in which AI attitude improvement will be achieved through professional knowledge development. That underlines the need for continuous training covering not only technical competencies but also ethical considerations and pedagogical applications of AI in education. This weak correlation also shows that there might be other influential factors affecting attitudes toward AI. Other factors that can influence attitudes at the institutional, peer-influence, and personal experience levels concerning AI tools include support within an institutional setting (Lukianets & Lukianets, 2023). Further research may investigate other factors influencing the attitudes toward AI to extend the model of AI acceptance in higher education.

While the study reflects quite a high level of knowledge concerning integrating AI-based tools into ethical considerations, more discussion needs to be carried out regarding the ethical implications of AI in education. To be sure, as AI is increasingly the driver in higher education, particular attention needs to be placed on data privacy, bias in algorithms, and issues that might further widen inequity. The timeliness of this present study that focuses on ethical integration is, therefore, opportune, because there are now growing misgivings over the ethical implications of AI in education. Eaton et al. (2022) discuss how AI has the potential to compromise academic integrity, especially in areas like assessment and plagiarism detection. If educators are to further develop their knowledge and skills in AI integration, ethical considerations must remain at the forefront of these efforts.

The findings of this study have significant implications for professional development programs and institutional policies regarding integrating AI into higher education. The high levels of knowledge and positive attitudes characteristic of the environment are indicative of a favorable environment for AI-

related initiatives. However, this weak linkage between knowledge and attitudes presents evidence that knowledge per se is an insufficient driver of the adoption and effective use of AI tools. Tsai et al. (2019) identified a higher education AI literacy framework involving technical skills, social impacts, and ethics. Based on the results of this present study, it is recommended that institutions take such an all-rounded framework for the programs undertaken at workplaces. Training should go more toward ethical considerations besides technical knowledge and be directed more toward practical applications within disciplines, and hands-on experience in using the AI tools.

Conclusion

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the current state of AI integration in higher education from the perspective of instructors. The high levels of professional knowledge and positive attitudes observed are encouraging signs for the future of AI in education. However, the weak correlation between knowledge and attitudes, as well as the lack of significant differences across experience levels and disciplines, warrant further investigation.

Future research should explore the specific factors that contribute to the development of professional knowledge and positive attitudes toward AI in education. Longitudinal studies could provide insights into how these variables change over time as AI technologies continue to evolve and become more prevalent in educational settings. Additionally, qualitative studies exploring educators' experiences and perceptions could provide deeper insights into the challenges and opportunities of AI integration.

As AI continues to transform the landscape of higher education, it is crucial to maintain a focus on ethical integration and effective pedagogical practices. By building on the foundations of knowledge and positive attitudes revealed in this study, higher education institutions can work towards harnessing the full potential of AI to enhance teaching and learning experiences while addressing important ethical and societal considerations.

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